

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION
OF EMTRICITABINE AND TENOFOVIR DISOPROXIL
FUMARATE DRUGS TO QUANTITATE BY RP-HPLC****V. Mounika*, J. Hanna Blessy, Dr. Nagaraju Pappula, G. Indira Priyadarshini**Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh,
India**Abstract:**

A reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatographic method (RP-HPLC) was developed to determine Emtricitabine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate in combined and tablet doses. Separation is carried out by using waters - HPLC system equipped with 1200 series isocratic pump; Rheodyne injector with 20 µl fixed volume loop, PDA detector, Inspire C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm) column, used phosphate buffer (pH -6.8)- acetonitrile in gradient mode at flow rate of 0.25 ml/min used as a mobile phase and detection is carried out at 257nm at ambient temperature. The active pharmaceutical ingredient is extracted from the tablet dosage form using a mixture of phosphate buffer and acetonitrile (40:60) as a diluent. The calibration graphs were linear, and the method showed excellent recoveries in the tablet dosage form. The developed HPLC method was validated and meets the requirements delineated by the International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines concerning linearity, accuracy, precision, and robustness. The intra-day and inter-day variation was found to be less than 1%. The method was reproducible and selective for estimating Emtricitabine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate.

Keywords: Rp-Hplc, Emtricitabine, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate.

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Please cite this article in press V. Mounika al., Analytical Method Development And Validation Of Emtricitabine And Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate Drugs To Quantitate By Rp-Hplc, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(06).

1. INTRODUCTION:

Emtricitabine, with the trade name **Emtriva**, is a [nucleosidereverse-transcriptase inhibitor](#) (NRTI) for the prevention and treatment of [HIV](#) infection in adults and children. It is used in combination therapy for the treatment of HIV-1 infection. It has a role as an antiviral drug and an HIV-1 reverse transcriptase inhibitor. It is a pyrimidone, an organo-fluorine compound. Chemical name 4-amino-5-fluoro-1-[(2R,5S)-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-yl]1, dihydropyrimidin-2-one. Molecular formula C₈H₁₀FN₃O₃S, Molecular mass 247.248g/mol, Soluble in water and methanol, and soluble in Acetonitrile.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Emtricitabine

[disoproxil](#) and [fumaric acid](#). It is used in combination therapy for the treatment of HIV infection. It has a role as a prodrug, an HIV-1 reverse transcriptase inhibitor, and an antiviral drug. It contains [tenofovir disoproxil](#).

Molecular formula C₂₃H₃₄N₅O₁₄P. Molecular Weight 635.5 g/mol. Soluble in water, 13.4 mg/mL at 25 °C. Chemical name ([(2R)-1-(6-amino-9H-purin-9-yl)propan-2-yl]oxy)methyl phosphonic acid. Molecular formula C₉H₁₄N₅O₄P. Molecular mass 287.213g/mol. Soluble in water and methanol and freely soluble in acetonitrile.

Figure 2: Chemical structure of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate

Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate is a fumarate salt prepared from equimolar amounts of [tenofovir](#)

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Optimized chromatographic conditions of Emtricitabine and Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate

Standard Concentration	Emtricitabine 200 µg/mL	
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate 300 µg/mL	
Pump mode	Isocratic	
Mobile phase	10 mM phosphate buffer (pH-6.8): Acetonitrile 40:60 (v/v)	
Wavelength	260 nm	
Column	Phenomenex-Luna C18 column (250x4.6 mm, 5 µm)	
Column Temp	Ambient	
Diluent	Mobile Phase	
Injector	Rheodyne	
Injection Volume	20 µL	
Flow rate	1 mL/min	
Retention Time	Emtricitabine	2.86 min
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	7.40 min
Runtime	9 min	
Peak Area	Emtricitabine	111120
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	83013
Theoretical plates	Emtricitabine	8569
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	9577
Tailing Factor	Emtricitabine	0.07
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	0.32
Resolution	Emtricitabine	-
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	5.61

3-Blank chromatogram

Fig-

Fig-4-Standard chromatogram of Emtricitabine and Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate

Fig-5-Test formulation chromatogram: Emtricitabine and Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate

3. RESULTS:

Table-1:-Specificity of ETB and TDF

Name of the solution	Retention Time(min)
Blank	No peaks
Emtricitabine	2.86min
Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	7.40min

Table-2: System suitability results of ETB and TDF

Retention Time	Emtricitabine	2.84min
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	7.40min
Peak Area	Emtricitabine	111223
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	83213
Theoretical plates	Emtricitabine	8569
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	9577
Tailing Factor	Emtricitabine	0.07
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	0.32
Resolution	Emtricitabine	-
	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	5.61

Table -3: Linearity and range of ETB and TDF

S.No.	Concentration $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	Area of Emtricitabine	Concentration $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	Area of Tenofovir
1	40	22988	60	16998
2	80	47605	120	31602
3	120	68028	180	50459
4	160	90704	240	67137
5	200	112120	300	84014
6	240	130654	360	101710
Concentration range	40-240 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$		60-360 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	
Slope(m)	547		282	
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9987		0.9995	

Fig. 6: Linearity of Emtricitabine

Fig 7: Linearity of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate

Table-4: Intra day precision data for ETB and TDF

Sample.No	Area of ETB	%Assay	Area of TDF	% Assay
1	110164	100.59	84015	99.11
2	110145	100.57	84037	99.14
3	111162	101.50	84052	99.16
4	111133	101.47	84062	99.17
5	110152	100.58	84034	99.13
6	111160	101.50	84014	99.11
Mean	110653	101.03	84036	99.14
SD	546.76	0.50	19.29	0.02
%RSD	0.49	0.49	0.02	0.02

Table-5: Inter day precision data for ETB and TDF

Sample.No	Area of ETB	%Assay	Area of TDF	% Assay
1	110165	100.59	85031	99.54
2	110138	100.56	85137	99.93
3	110222	100.64	85012	100.35
4	110142	100.57	85034	99.76
5	110163	100.59	84511	100.43
6	110122	100.55	85038	99.99
Mean	110159	100.58	84961	100.00
SD	34.98	0.03	224.60	0.34
%RSD	0.03	0.03	0.26	0.34

Table-6. Accuracy of ETB

Level of % recovery	Target Conc.($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Amount of drug spiked($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Nominal conc($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Drug recovered($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	% Recovery	Mean	SD	% RSD
80	80	64.00	144.00	144.65	100.45	100.11	0.61	0.61
				143.14	99.40			
				144.67	100.47			
100	80	80.00	160.00	160.89	100.56	100.17	0.39	0.39
				160.27	100.17			
				159.64	99.78			
120	80	96.00	176.00	176.12	100.07	100.06	0.07	0.07
				175.97	99.98			
				176.22	100.13			

Table-7.Accuracy of TDF

Level of % recovery	Target Conc.($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount of drug spiked($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Nominal conc($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Drug covered($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	Mean	SD	%RSD
80	120	96.00	216.00	216.19	100.09	100.03	0.05	0.05
				215.98	99.99			
				216.05	100.02			
100	120	120.00	240.00	241.06	100.44	100.28	0.18	0.18
				240.74	100.31			
				240.22	100.09			
120	120	144.00	264.00	263.26	99.72	100.09	0.36	0.36
				265.14	100.43			
				264.32	100.12			

Table-8.Ruggedness of ETB &TDF

S.No	ETB(% Assay)			TDF(% Assay)		
	SETI	SETII	SETIII	SETI	SETII	SETIII
1	101.60	101.31	99.40	98.32	100.51	98.70
2	98.60	99.45	99.70	98.43	100.45	99.70
3	101.90	99.25	99.55	99.21	100.55	98.65
4	101.40	99.67	98.60	99.17	100.64	99.43
5	101.60	100.11	98.20	99.32	100.11	99.22
6	99.50	100.16	99.76	98.06	99.48	99.96
Mean	100.77	99.99	99.20	98.75	100.29	99.28
SD	1.37	0.74	0.65	0.54	0.44	0.53
%RSD	1.36	0.74	0.65	0.55	0.44	0.53
Overall Average	99.99			99.44		
Overall %RSD	1.36			0.55		

Table-9.Robustness of ETB &TDF

S.NO	Parameter	Condition	ETB		TDF	
			Area(n=3)	%change	Area(n=3)	%change
1	Standard	Standard conditions	112120	0	84014	0
2	Mobile Phase composition($\pm 2\%$)	10mM phosphate buffer(pH-6.8):Acetonitrile;(38:62,v/v)	112232	-0.100	84054	-0.048
		10mM phosphate buffer(pH-6.8):Acetonitrile;(42:58,v/v)	112262	-0.027	84084	-0.036
3	Mobile phase pH(± 0.2 units)	6.6	111232	0.917	84034	0.059
		7.0	112157	-0.832	84036	-0.002
4	Wavelength (nm)(± 2 nm)	258	111162	0.887	84042	-0.007
		262	112165	-0.902	84035	0.008
5	Flow rate(mL) ± 0.2 mL	1.2	111169	0.888	84042	-0.008
		0.8	111165	0.004	84040	0.002

Table-10.LOD and LOQ of ETB &TDF

Parameter	ETB	TDF
LOD($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	5.888	0.225
LOQ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	17.841	0.683

Table-11. Solution Stability of ETB at room temperature

Time	Standard stock			Test stock		
	Fresh	Stability Stock	%Diff.	Fresh	Stability Stock	%Diff.
Initial	102232	102232	NA	102232	102231	NA
6h	102151	102157	-0.006	102155	102153	0.002
12h	102164	102162	0.002	102162	101162	0.979
20h	102168	102161	0.007	102165	102167	-0.002
26h	102162	102167	-0.005	102167	101167	0.979
30h	102166	102162	0.004	102162	102152	0.010
36h	102167	102175	-0.008	102165	102164	0.001

Table-12. Solution Stability of TDF at room temperature

Time	Standard stock			Test stock		
	Fresh	Stability Stock	%Diff.	Fresh	Stability Stock	%Diff.
Initial	84052	84052	NA	84052	84052	NA
6h	84047	84045	0.002	84045	84047	-0.002
12h	84052	84057	-0.006	84052	83052	1.190
20h	84066	84068	-0.002	84066	84057	0.011
26h	84058	84258	-0.238	84058	84047	0.013
30h	84052	84022	0.036	84052	84152	-0.119
36h	84056	84156	-0.119	84056	84042	0.017

Table-13. Solution Stability of ETB at Refrigerated Temperature

Time	Standard stock			Test stock		
	Fresh	Stability Stock	%Diff.	Fresh	Stability Stock	%Diff.
Initial	102237	102244	NA	102233	102233	NA
6h	102156	102166	-0.010	102150	102155	-0.005
12h	102162	102132	0.029	102162	102362	-0.196
20h	102165	102168	-0.003	102164	102167	-0.003
26h	102169	102160	0.009	102166	102169	-0.003
30h	102162	102121	0.040	102162	102160	0.002
36h	102160	102175	-0.015	102164	102161	0.003

Table-14.SolutionStability of TDF at Refrigerated Temperature

Time	Standard stock			Test stock		
	Fresh	Stability Stock	%Diff.	Fresh	Stability Stock	%Diff.
Initial	84053	84043	NA	84023	84033	NA
6h	84047	84036	0.013	84746	84086	0.779
12h	84058	84091	-0.039	84052	84054	-0.002
20h	84070	84064	0.007	84070	84068	0.002
26h	84052	84037	0.018	84054	84037	0.020
30h	84052	84252	-0.238	84053	84056	-0.004
36h	84058	84077	-0.023	84053	84051	0.002

Table-15.Filter Interference Results for ETB &TDF

ETB				
Filtration Method	Centrifuged	Nylon	PTFE	PVDF
Area(Inj.1)	102234	102233	102232	102232
Area(Inj.2)	102152	102113	102158	102155
Avg.Area	102193	102173	102195	102194
%Difference		0.020	-0.022	0.001
TDF				
Filtration Method	Centrifuged	Nylon	PTFE	PVDF
Area(Inj.1)	84052	84062	84053	84052
Area(Inj.2)	84042	84052	84046	84057
Avg.Area	84047	84057	84049.5	84054.5
%Difference		-0.012	0.009	-0.006

4. CONCLUSION:

The present work compiled with initial research objectives and successfully demonstrated the applicability of RP-HPLC for pharmaceutical analysis of different classes of drugs, namely Emtricitabine and Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate, in pharmaceutical formulations by RP-HPLC with UV detection. The developed and validated methods showed a high degree of sensitivity, selectivity, reproducibility, and good recovery, stability with negligible matrix effects when compared with previously reported methods.

This research work has contributions in two important scientific fields.

- ✓ From an analytical research and development (AR&D) point of view, useful for analytical research scientists, particularly for developing new analytical methods for these selected drugs.
- ✓ From a drug regulatory point of view, the generated data meets regulatory standards, and it is acceptable for regulatory submission.

The tremendous potential of RP-HPLC for

pharmaceutical analysis is evident. It will unquestionably expand future research capabilities in terms of shorter run times, high ruggedness, and reproducibility of analytical methods with high precision and accuracy.

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